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ONLINE WEB TOOL FOR PERFORMING HMM SEARCHES

D2.5

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1. Scope of Deliverable

From the Grant Agreement: *“This deliverable will consist in an online semi-automatic web tool for performing Hidden-Markov-Model (HMM) search for sequences of interest. More in details, will consist in a publicly available user-friendly and open-source semi-automatic informatic tool for screening, through Hidden-Markov-Model (HMM) searches, full length chain sequences encoding enzymes relevant to FuturEnzyme from public repositories. The tool will be accompanied by a report detailing the functioning of the tool and the scores, e-values, sequence identities, sequence coverages, etc., applied.”*

2. Executive Summary

This deliverable introduces AHATool, an automated, user-friendly platform for advanced protein sequence screening using profile Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). Originally developed as a command-line pipeline, AHATool was packaged as a Docker container and integrated into the Horus workflow manager by BSC for improved accessibility and ease of use.

AHATool allows researchers to analyze both public and private datasets, detecting remote homologs with high sensitivity and leveraging comprehensive resources like Pfam/InterPro. Within Horus, users can easily upload input files, select databases, and adjust key parameters through an intuitive web interface, seamlessly integrating sequence screening into broader bioinformatics workflows.

No significant deviations from the original plan occurred, aside from its integration in Horus, which enhances stability and usability. AHATool in Horus now provides the scientific community with a robust, scalable, and efficient solution for protein annotation and discovery.

3. Introduction/Background

The exponential growth of public and private sequence databases, including both genomes and metagenomes, propelled by advancements in high-throughput sequencing technologies, has vastly increased opportunities for protein annotation and discovery. However, this progress simultaneously poses challenges for accurately identifying homologous relationships, annotating novel sequences, and discerning functionally important features. Within this context, HMMs have emerged as a powerful and sensitive tool for sequence comparison and annotation, offering notable advantages over traditional pairwise methods.

HMMs are probabilistic models originally developed in the late 1960s for speech and signal processing. They quickly gained popularity in bioinformatics as foundational techniques for aligning and profiling protein and nucleotide sequences. Conceptually, an HMM models biological sequences as a series of hidden "states" (such as conserved or variable positions in a protein family), each emitting observable residues with defined probabilities (**Figure 1**). This allows HMMs to capture the position-specific conservation patterns within sequence families, providing the basis for profile HMMs. In fact, the mathematical concepts behind HMMs contributed significantly to the emergence of modern machine learning, laying groundwork for probabilistic inference and model training.

Figure 1. HMM logo of a protein domain. The logo shows amino acid conservation at each alignment position, with taller stacks indicating higher conservation. Letter size reflects residue frequency. Occupancy frequencies show how often each position is present in sequences. Insert probability and insert length plots indicate where and how frequently insertions occur in the alignment. Created with Skylign (Wheeler et al., 2014).

In the context of protein analysis, profile HMM searches have several distinct advantages over heuristic pairwise alignment approaches such as BLAST. While BLAST compares a query sequence directly to individual database sequences, profile HMMs compare queries to statistical models constructed from multiple sequence alignments, capturing the conserved patterns and variability within entire protein families (**Figure 2**). This model-based approach greatly increases sensitivity for detecting distant homologs, as profile HMMs are better able to recognize remote evolutionary relationships that might escape detection by pairwise methods. Additionally, profile HMMs explicitly model insertions and deletions, making them more robust when analyzing sequences with gaps or length variation. Modern HMM search algorithms also employ efficient prefiltering and computational optimizations, which can result in faster screening of large databases, particularly when searching for motifs or domains across vast amounts of sequence data. A prime example is the Pfam database (Paysan-Lafosse et al., 2025), since 2022 hosted by InterPro (Blum et al., 2025), which makes available over 24,000 curated HMMs representing protein families and domains; this extensive resource enables comprehensive and sensitive annotation of protein sequences on a global scale. Thus, profile HMM searches are often used by annotation software such as Prokka (Seemann 2014).

Figure 2. Path through a profile HMM diagram. The profile HMM transforms a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) into system with scores for each position within the MSA, in order to model a hidden path with respect to the conserved sequence motifs. The given amino acids are encoded and ordered accordingly. Deletions and insertions, two kinds of observed stochastic processes, are represented differently in the profile HMM (examples encircled in red) and the path through the graph is created optimally for the specific profile HMM. It is then decided whether the query protein belongs to the family represented in the profile HMM. ©Nele Schulte, UHAM.

Despite their versatility, current online HMM search platforms have limitations. For example, the HMMER web server hosted by EMBL-EBI (Potter et al., 2018) allows users to screen against UniProtKB, SwissProt, PDB, or AlphaFold, but it does not support NCBI's non-redundant, custom or private sequence databases, such as those derived from metagenome projects or unpublished datasets. This restricts users who wish to screen novel, proprietary, or non-public data for proteins of interest.

To address these gaps, UHAM, in collaboration with BSC, developed a user-friendly tool for HMM-based protein sequence screening, supporting both public datasets and secure, private data uploads. Initial versions operated locally through a series of scripts to automate software calls, parse inputs and outputs, and generate unified results. The tool was then redeveloped by BSC as a Docker container, improving deployment, reproducibility, and compatibility across diverse systems. For increased usability and practicality, it was ultimately integrated into the free-to-use multi-platform workflow manager Horus (<https://horus.bsc.es/>) developed by BSC within FuturEnzyme (**Deliverable D2.6**), allowing more seamless and efficient access for users.

4. AHATool - an Automated HMM search and Analysis Tool

The initial versions of AHATool were developed as a command-line-based software pipeline for automated protein sequence analysis using profile Hidden Markov Models (HMMs). The tool was programmed and executed in a Linux environment and designed to automate and unify a multi-step workflow, streamlining tasks that traditionally involved multiple independent bioinformatics tools (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Overview of the components of AHATool. The tools and functionalities seen above are were inspired by the initial design. The two sources of input lead to different output formats and content. Essential for the structural analysis are the creation of a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) and a profile HMM. The hits from the profile HMM search are used for the creation of a summary table which is additionally fed with information gathered through SignalP (Teufel et al., 2022). Furthermore, an analysis of the signal peptides provides the user with a mature fasta file. When using a custom DB, BLASTp is used to identify the organism of origin for the hit sequences. In either case the taxonomy is added to the summary table using epost. Blue: descriptions; dark-grey: integrated tools.

The pipeline encompasses several stages: first, known protein sequences provided by the user are aligned into a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) using T-Coffee (Notredame et al., 2000). This alignment serves as input for HMMER’s `hmmbuild` to create a profile HMM (Mistry et al., 2013), encapsulating the patterns of conservation and variation present in the aligned sequences. The constructed HMM is then employed via HMMER’s `hmmsearch` to scan large sequence databases—such as NCBI’s non-redundant (nr) protein database (Sayers et al., 2025) or custom user-provided datasets—to identify homologous sequences.

Following sequence detection, the tool incorporates additional analysis steps for biological characterization. For example, SignalP (Teufel et al., 2022) is invoked to predict protein secretion peptides, and taxonomy information for identified hits is retrieved using NCBI’s E-utilities or BLASTp (Sayers et al., 2025), depending on the database and analysis pathway. Each step in the process is executed using dedicated scripts, which also parse and reformat input and output files as required to ensure seamless data flow between the tools.

A principal innovation of AHATool is the automated handling of intermediate outputs, enabling standardized and reproducible summary tables. These final outputs consolidate the key findings—such as sequence scores, annotation, taxonomy, and predicted features—into comprehensive, user-friendly reports.

The tool was implemented as a set of modular, interlinked scripts organized through a clear folder structure and controlled by a main driver script. Various auxiliary scripts manage job parameters, database updating, and error handling. The pipeline was designed to be broadly applicable, allowing users to submit any input protein family or database of interest. Testing and optimization focused on robustness, reproducibility, and minimizing manual intervention.

In summary, the programming of the first versions of AHATool provided a fully automated, script-based workflow for deep protein sequence analysis with profile HMMs, integrating external open-source tools through command-line scripting to produce standardized, comprehensive analysis outputs for any target protein set.

5. Implementation of AHATool in Horus

To increase both accessibility and usability, it was essential to transition AHATool from a collection of command-line scripts to an online, user-friendly platform. The first step in this process, already accomplished in **Milestone MS7**, was to package all necessary scripts and third-party software into a single, portable container. For this, Docker was chosen, a widely-used platform that enables consistent and reproducible deployment across diverse computing environments. The package can be accessed and downloaded for local use here:

- <https://hub.docker.com/r/bsceapm/ahatool>
- <https://github.com/BSC-CNS-EAPM/AHATool-container/tree/main>

After containerizing AHATool, it became clear that the tool would be an ideal component for integration within the bioprospecting workflow manager Horus, which is being developed by BSC (**Deliverable D2.6**, <https://horus.bsc.es/>). Horus is designed to streamline and coordinate complex bioinformatics analyses, making it possible for users to construct workflows from modular components.

BSC integrated the AHATool Docker module as a block within the Horus platform. The AHATool module requires two primary inputs: (1) a protein FASTA file or a pre-existing HMM file, and (2) a sequence database for screening (**Figure 4**). If a multifasta file is provided, the module automatically performs a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) and then builds the corresponding profile HMM before starting the search. If an HMM file is given instead, AHATool directly initiates an HMM search (hmmsearch) against the selected database.

Figure 4. Integration of AHATool in the Horus Workflow. This figure shows the AHATool module as a workflow block within Horus, connected to two input blocks: one providing the FASTA file (or HMM) containing protein sequences of interest, and the other supplying the target database. This structure illustrates how users can visually link data sources to AHATool within the online workflow environment for streamlined sequence analysis.

To enhance user control and adaptability, several options are available in the Horus block menu for the AHATool module (**Figure 5**). Users can specify a custom filename prefix for output files, adjust the e-value threshold for search sensitivity, and set the number of threads for parallel execution, allowing for efficient use of available computational resources.

Figure 5. AHATool Module Options in Horus. Users can set various parameters, including the filename prefix for output files, the e-value threshold for search sensitivity, and the number of threads to use for parallel processing. These customizable options enable users to tailor their HMM search and analysis workflows directly within the user-friendly Horus interface.

In summary, the integration of AHATool into Horus has enabled seamless online access to advanced HMM-based protein sequence screening, offering a streamlined workflow with minimal setup and user-friendly controls.

6. Deviations from Description of Action (DoA)

There was no significant deviation from the DoA, other than the integration of the tool into the Horus workflow manager. We believe this integration represents a clear improvement in terms of accessibility and stability, while also enabling users to seamlessly combine the output of HMM searches with other workflows within Horus. This allows for more advanced downstream analyses, such as deeper structural assessment, to further refine the selection of hits and identify the best candidates for each specific purpose.

7. Conclusions

The development and integration of a user-friendly HMM-based protein sequence screening tool into the Horus workflow manager addresses key limitations in current sequence analysis solutions. By supporting both public and private datasets, and leveraging comprehensive databases such as Pfam/InterPro, the tool offers researchers a sensitive, robust, and accessible platform for protein annotation and homology searches. Integration within Horus not only enhances accessibility and long-term stability but also enables seamless incorporation of HMM search results into complex analytic pipelines, including advanced structural and functional analyses. Overall, this deliverable provides the scientific community with a versatile and efficient resource for high-quality protein sequence analysis, adaptable to a wide range of research applications. With the information described herein, we can conclude that this deliverable is achieved.

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